

A new cytoplasmic male sterile line, IR69700 A, has the cytoplasm of *O. glumaepatula* and nuclear background of IR64.

backcrossed with the recurrent parent. Of all the backcross derivatives, one line with *O. glumaepatula* (Acc 100969) cytoplasm was found to be stable for complete pollen sterility (see table). This line was designated as IR69700 A. Earlier, we developed a CMS line (IR66707 A) with *O. perennis* (Acc 104823) cytoplasm and the nuclear genome of IR64.

Crosses of IR69700A with nine restorers of WA cytoplasm show almost complete (88-100%) pollen sterility, indicating that the male sterility source of IR69700 A is different from WA cytoplasm. The new CMS line is now in BC10 and resembles maintainer IR69700 B in morphological characters, except that it flowers 5-7 d later (see figure). This line is completely sterile and does not set any seed upon selfing. We are searching for restorers of this male sterile line for use in hybrid rice breeding. ■

Pattern of segregation for grain weight involving bold and slender-grained rice varieties

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Fine-grained rice varieties are generally preferred in the market and sell for a premium price. Grain weight determines the fineness of the grain. We evaluated the pattern of segregation for grain weight in the F₂ generation for four parents: TKM 9 (short bold), IR50 (long slender), White Ponni (medium slender), and Pusa Basmati 1 (extra long slender) with contrasting grain types.

We grew 30 plants for each replication of P₁, P₂, and F₁ in two 3-m rows and 120 plants of F₂ in eight rows during 1992 dry

Pattern of segregation for hundred-grain weight in F₂ progenies.

season. The trial was replicated three times. One seedling hill⁻¹ was planted using a spacing of 30 × 30 cm. Ten plants replication⁻¹ in P₁, P₂, and F₁ and 70 plants replication⁻¹ in F₂ were evaluated for hundred-grain weight.

Among the parents, White Ponni possessed the least grain weight (0.016 g). The F₁ was intermediate between the parents in two crosses and exceeded the parental limits in IR50/Pusa Basmati 1. All crosses showed transgressive segregation for grain weight in both directions. White Ponni/Pusa Basmati 1 recorded the least mean grain weight in F₁ and F₂ generations with a high coefficient of variation (see table). It possessed high frequency (45 plants) of fine-grained segregants (0.014-0.017 g) and offers scope for selection. The cross involving bold- and slender-grained varieties (TKM9/Pusa Basmati 1) registered high frequency of progenies with grain weight of more than 0.022 g (see figure). ■

Mean performance, range, and coefficient of variation for hundred-grain weight.

Cross combination	Mean					Range (g)	CV (%)
	Pistil parent	Pollen parent	F ₁	F ₂			
TKM9/Pusa Basmati 1	2.41 + 0.01	1.88 + 0.01	2.11 + 0.02	2.13 + 0.01	1.6 - 2.8	9.44	
IR50/Pusa Basmati 1	1.80 + 0.01	1.88 + 0.01	1.98 + 0.02	1.94 + 0.01	1.6 - 2.5	8.15	
White Ponni/Pusa Basmati 1	1.67 + 0.01	1.88 + 0.01	1.79 + 0.01	1.76 + 0.01	1.4 - 2.3	10.40	